

Possibility of Covering All the Power Demand in the Island of Crete, Greece with Solar Photovoltaics

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ABSTRACT:

The increasing use of solar energy for heat and power generation, particular in areas with high solar irradiance like in Mediterranean region, is very important for the mitigation of climate change and the achievement of net-zero emission societies. The size of the solar photovoltaic systems which could meet all the electricity demand in Crete, Greece and the required land area for their installation have been evaluated taking into account the electricity demand in the island in 2025. Our results indicate that the nominal power of the solar photovoltaics which could meet all the power demand in 2025 in Crete is 2,333 MWp while their installation cost is 2.33 bill. € or 2,333 €/capita. The required land area for the installation of the abovementioned solar photovoltaic systems is 4,660 ha or 7.5 m²/capita which corresponds at 0.56% of the total surface of Crete. Our findings indicate that electricity self-sufficiency with zero carbon impacts in the island of Crete can be achieved with the use of the local solar energy resources while the necessary land area for the installation of the benign energy generation systems consists of only a small percentage of the island's surface. The results could be useful to policy makers and the local authorities in the island who are interested in achieving energy security and self-sufficiency combined with carbon neutrality in power generation.

Keywords: Crete-Greece, land coverage, photovoltaic, power demand, solar energy.

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INTRODUCTION

The generation of solar power is increasing worldwide for many reasons while it is foreseen that a significant amount of the global electricity demand in 2050 will be met with solar energy systems [1]. The installation of solar power systems on valuable land areas creates conflicts with other land area uses for food and animal feed production as well as for land protection [2], [3], [4], [5]. Mediterranean basin is a privileged region for generation of solar electricity due to the high solar irradiance [6]. The advantages of using solar photovoltaics in islands have been highlighted [7], [8], [9]. Apart from the current practice of mounting solar photovoltaic (solar-PV) panels on the ground several alternative solutions have been proposed for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems minimizing the use of valuable land. They include the use of: a) floating solar-PVs [10], [11], b) agrivoltaics [3], [12], c) vertical photovoltaics [13], [14], and d) bifacial photovoltaics [15]. The land area requirements for the installation of solar power systems in several territories worldwide have been estimated [16], [17], [18].

The aim of the current work is the estimation of the land area requirements for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems meeting all the electricity demand in the island of Crete, Greece.

The paper is structured as follows: After the literature survey the solar photovoltaic technology, including novel solar-PV systems, is shortly stated. Next, the electricity demand in Crete is evaluated followed by an estimation of the required land area for the installation of solar photovoltaics meeting

all the power demand in 2025 in Crete. The text ends with discussion of the findings, the conclusions drawn and the citation of the references used.

The current work could be useful to policy makers, to local authorities, to farmers, to energy companies and to potential investors in solar photovoltaic technology. It covers an existing gap related with the future use of valuable land area in Crete for solar electricity generation additionally to agricultural production and the land area preservation. It is also innovative giving insight in new solar-PV systems which potentially could minimize the use of land areas for solar-PV electricity generation in the island.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The regional potential for solar power generation in EU-28 has been assessed [2]. The authors developed a preliminary suitability map for the installation of large-scale solar-PV systems in EU countries. They proposed the use of degraded and contaminated land for the installation of large-scale photovoltaic plants avoiding the use of valuable agricultural land. The solar energy status in the world has been reviewed [1]. The authors stated that the contribution of solar energy to global electricity generation is still low at 3.6% while it is the second most installed renewable energy resource behind hydropower. They also mentioned that solar energy could generate approximately 25% of the world's total electricity demand by 2050. The floating photovoltaic systems and the energy storage methods have been reviewed [10]. The authors stated that floating photovoltaics (FPV) have the potential to significantly increase the efficiency and reliability of renewable energy generation worldwide. They also mentioned that the countries with the highest potential for installation of FPV are USA, China, Brazil, India and Canada. The electricity generation in Crete in 2018 was 3,042.8 GWh while the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the energy mix was at 21.2 % [19]. The required land area for the installation of various renewable energy systems has been estimated [16]. It is stated that flat-plate solar photovoltaic technology is the most land-efficient renewable energy technology to generate green energy. It is also mentioned that the land area required for installation of solar-PV systems per GWp is in the range of 10-50 km²/GWp while the required land area per generated GWh is at 5,000-23,000 m²/GWh. The floating solar photovoltaic technology has been reviewed [11]. The authors stated that although the world is transitioning towards a net-zero emissions future the land requirements for installing solar farms present a barrier due to the increase of population density and the rise of land prices. They mentioned that FPV is a promising solution to land scarcity estimating that coverage of 1% of global water reservoirs with FPV would have a potential capacity of 404 GWp. The global trends in agrivoltaic systems combining crops production and energy generation in the same place achieving the dual use of land have been studied [20]. They authors mentioned that the majority of the relevant scientific publications were concentrated in the last three years. The use of solar power plants for achieving energy autonomy in the island of Mykonos, Greece has been examined [17]. The authors assuming that the annual electricity generation of tilted solar-PV systems in Mykonos-island is 2,036.04 KWh/m² estimated that a solar-PV system with nominal power at 120 MWp could cover all the annual energy demand in the island. They also evaluated that the solar-PV system will cover an area at 2,426,748 m² corresponding at 2.8% of the island's surface. The potential and the challenges of agrivoltaics in the European Union have been examined [12]. The authors stated that agrivoltaics allow the continuation of agricultural activities. They also estimated that coverage of only 1% of the utilized agricultural area in EU with agrivoltaics corresponds at 944 GWp which is approximately five times more than the installed solar-PV capacity in EU in 2022. The multidimensional role of agrivoltaics in the era of the EU green deal has been reviewed [3]. The authors stated that one core pillar for the green energy transition in Mediterranean countries is the solar photovoltaic power. In this context the "symbiosis" of food and energy under the same land is important. They also mentioned that agrivoltaics decrease the evapotranspiration rate in crops reducing the water demand for irrigation which is important in areas with water scarcity. The advantages and the challenges of FPV have been studied [21]. The authors stated that if 1% of the surface of the world's water reservoirs will be covered by FPV the installed solar power would be increased by 404 GWp. They also mentioned that the effect of FPV on water quality and on aquatic life is still not well known. The impact of solar-PV systems on farming has been investigated [4]. The author stated that solar power installations can boost crop's yield, save

water and protect the biodiversity. He also mentioned the advantages of FPV and agrivoltaics. The potential land requirements for the installation of solar energy systems in EU, India, Japan and South Korea have been evaluated [18]. The authors stated that a 25-80 % penetration of solar electricity in the energy mix in these regions by 2050 will require the occupation of 0.5-5 % of the total land area with solar energy systems. They also mentioned that the land cover changes will cause a net-release of carbon in the range of 0 to 50 grCO₂/KWh depending on various parameters. According to a market-research related to agrivoltaics [22], USA is lagging behind Europe and Asia-Pacific region in the adoption of this technology. It is stated that agrivoltaics allow the simultaneous use of land for both agriculture and power generation while they can be used with livestock as well as with fruit and vegetable production. The opportunities and challenges of bifacial photovoltaics (BPV) have been investigated [15]. The authors stated that BPV have many advantages and they are going to prevail in the solar-PV market. They also mentioned that the gain of energy yield of BPV can be up to 5-15% on a flat roof while in several cases it could reach up to 30%. The BPV technology has been reviewed [23]. The authors stated that a BPV system can offer 25-30% additional power compared to a conventional solar-PV system. They also mentioned that BPV can be installed on the ground, on cultivated crops, on water bodies and on rooftops of buildings. The use of FPV on water reservoirs in Crete, Greece has been studied [24]. The author estimated that covering 10% of the major water bodies in the island with FPV significant amount of electricity could be generated at 46.37 GWh/year corresponding at 1.52% of the annual power demand in Crete. The performance of bifacial solar-PV modulus in Brazil has been studied [25]. The authors stated that more than 2/3 of the new solar power plants in Brazil are using bifacial PV modulus. They also mentioned that the power gain of the bifacial modulus compared to conventional solar-PV panels is in the range of 3-7 % for typical installations. The use of solar energy technologies in Mediterranean region has been studied [6]. The authors stated that the current status of solar energy technologies allow: a) The photovoltaic power generation in large-scale plants at low cost, b) The use of solar-PV and solar thermal technologies in several types of buildings, and c) The replacement of vehicles equipped with internal combustion engines with battery electric vehicles recharged with solar electricity. The performance of polycrystalline and monocrystalline PV technologies in a hot and arid region has been evaluated [26]. The authors stated that in areas with high solar radiation polycrystalline modules experienced a 14% decrease in power output compared to a 16% decrease in monocrystalline modules as the temperature increases. However, at low solar radiation the drop in power output in polycrystalline modules was 21% compared to 9% drop in monocrystalline modules. According to a report related with the development of solar-PV technology in Europe [27] solar photovoltaics were the fastest-growing technology for electricity generation among renewable energies in the past decade. It is also mentioned that the efficiency of solar-PV panels is gradually increasing while the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) is decreasing resulting in higher competitiveness in power generation. The performance of mono- and polycrystalline photovoltaic modules in east-central India has been evaluated [28]. The authors stated that monocrystalline modules performed better than the polycrystalline modules under all weather conditions. Although the cost of monocrystalline panels is higher than the cost of polycrystalline, the higher energy yields justify the higher investment cost. The advances in organic photovoltaic cells (OPV) have been studied [29]. The authors stated that OPV have the potential to revolutionize the solar energy industry due to their low production cost and their ability to produce thin, flexible solar cells. They also mentioned that OPV have several drawbacks including low energy efficiency, short durability and some technological limitations. The outdoor performance of organic photovoltaics has been assessed [30]. The authors stated that OPV cells represent an emerging and promising solution for low-cost energy production while they are flexible and semi-transparent. They also mentioned their disadvantages which limit their commercialization including their low efficiency, poor long-term stability and thermal issues. Various characteristics of the semi-transparent solar cells have been studied [31]. The authors stated that the development of semi-transparent PV cells allows the harvesting of solar energy through the windows and roofs of buildings and vehicles. They also mentioned that semi-transparent PV panels are currently based on silicon while the recent development of innovative organic and perovskite solar cells could offer new opportunities for power generation. The renewable energy projects in European isolated islands have been studied [7]. The authors stated that islands are considered as “test laboratories” for the development of RES. They mentioned that in these islands the high cost of energy generation from fossil fuels, the lack of grid

reliability and the abundance of RES favor the replacement of fossil fuels with renewable energies. A methodology for the promotion of solar-PV investments in small Italian islands has been developed [8]. The authors studied 20 Italian islands located in Mediterranean Sea focusing on the development of solar-PV installations with several configurations. They used the following three indicators for the assessment: a) penetration of RES (%), b) energy surplus (%), c) fuel consumption (lit/year). The difficulties of integrating solar-PV systems in French islands have been studied [9]. The authors stated that islands should promote the development of RES for economic and ecological reasons. They also mentioned that the Greek island Tilos is a very good example for developing a hybrid energy system consisted of solar-PVs, wind turbines and electric batteries. The optimization of the tilt angle in solar-PV systems has been investigated [32]. The author stated that the optimization of the tilt angle in solar-PV installations in Najaf city can improve the annual electricity yield by 18%. He also mentioned that the electricity gain is higher during the winter months while it is lower in summer months. The optimal tilt angle for solar-PV panels has been studied [33]. The authors stated that maximization of the energy yield in solar panels requires the use of motor tracking systems which are not cost-effective. They experimented with a solar-PV system of 5 KWp located in Chandigach, India. They mentioned that the tilt angle of a solar-PV system can be adjusted every three months per year to the optimal tilt angle increasing the annual electricity yield up to 7-8%. The optimum tilt angle adjustment in solar-PV systems in Europe has been investigated [34]. The authors stated that the monthly optimization of the tilt angle in solar-PV systems was the most effective solution achieving higher energy yield up to 7%. According to the Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate, 2023 [35] a significant growth of solar-PV systems in Greece is foreseen. The forecast for the installed solar photovoltaic capacity in Greece in 2020 is 40.3 GWp compared to 8.2 GWp in 2025. According to a report [36] solar energy could theoretically cover the world's electricity demand using only 0.3% of the global land area according to researchers in Aarhus university, Denmark. The researchers mentioned that vertical PVs, agrivoltaics and FPVs are going to grow rapidly in the future. The performance of vertically mounted photovoltaic modules has been studied [13]. The authors stated that the investment cost of bifacial vertical modules does not differ from the cost of conventional solar-PVs while for higher energy production the one face of the modules should be oriented towards the east while the other face towards the west. They also mentioned that the annual electricity generation from vertical solar-PV modules is at around 80-90% of the annual electricity generation of conventional solar-PV panels. The output characteristics of a vertical solar photovoltaic system in South Korea have been analyzed [14]. The authors investigated the performance of vertical bifacial PV modules facing east and west. They stated that the peak power of vertical bifacial PVs was around 80% of the peak power of conventional bifacial PVs. The solar energy development impacts on land cover change and protected areas with reference the state of California, USA have been studied [5]. The authors stated that the majority of utility-scale solar energy installations in California, USA are sited in natural environments. They mentioned that the land in California is used for energy, food and conservation goals while the opportunities for environmental co-benefits should be explored. The land area requirements of solar and wind power generation have been estimated [37]. The author stated that the potential space impacts of solar and wind energy systems depend on many factors and can vary widely while these systems are likely to need significantly more land area than other electricity generation installations. He also mentioned that developing a 100% renewable energy system would be challenging from a land use policy perspective. According to a report published by the University of Michigan, USA, [38] solar-PV systems, with intermediate efficiency, covering 0.6% of the land in USA would generate enough electricity to meet all the power demand in the country. The solar-PV potential in croplands has been assessed [39]. The author stated that there is a growing concern that large-scale solar energy installations might displace other land uses. They also mentioned that the efficiency of solar-PV panels depends on solar insolation, air temperature, wind speed and relative humidity. They proposed that agrivoltaics allow the dual use of land alleviating the land use competition. According to World Economic Forum [40] if solar-PV panels will be placed on the 50% of the world's rooftops they would meet the world's annual electricity demand. It is also mentioned that the potential hotspots for rooftop solar energy generation are located in Asia, North America and Europe.

SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC TECHNOLOGY

The use of solar photovoltaic systems for power generation is increasing due to the reduction of their installation cost and the decrease of the LCOE. Additionally, their reliability and maturity have been also improved. It is foreseen that in 2050 around 25% of the global power demand will be generated by solar photovoltaics [1]. The top ten countries in solar power installations are presented in table 1.

Table 1. The Top Ten Countries in Solar Power Installations

Country	Installed solar power (GWp)
China	393.0
USA	113.1
Japan	78.8
Germany	66.5
India	63.1
Australia	26.8
Italy	25.1
Brazil	24.1
Netherlands	22.6
South Korea	20.9

Source: [1]

The increasing global population and the increasing food demand combined with the requirements for climate change mitigation increase the installation of solar photovoltaic systems worldwide. Therefore, the conflicts related with the land area use for energy generation, food and feed production as well as for land preservation are increasing. In Mediterranean countries, which are characterized by high solar irradiance, the use of solar-PV technology has many advantages including: a) The low cost for large-scale solar power generation, b) The integration of solar photovoltaics in several types of buildings, and c) The use of electric vehicles with re-chargeable batteries powered by solar-PV electricity replacing the conventional vehicles using oil-based fuels.

Apart from the conventional solar-photovoltaic systems based on mono- and polycrystalline silicon and on thin film modules there are several new innovative photovoltaic systems including:

- a) Bifacial solar modules,
- b) Building integrated photovoltaics,
- c) Semi-transparent photovoltaics,
- d) Organic photovoltaics,
- e) Floating photovoltaics,
- f) Vertical solar modules, and
- g) Agrivoltaics.

Agrivoltaics combine the food production and the energy generation in the same land minimizing the conflicts related with the land use. Floating photovoltaics can be installed on existing water bodies covering a small part of their surface, usually less than 10%, avoiding their installation on valuable land. Bifacial solar modules can generate electricity from both sides of the panels having higher energy yields while their use is increasing. Vertical photovoltaics have satisfactory energy efficiencies requiring less space for their installation. Semi-transparent photovoltaics have applications in various sectors while they can be easily integrated in buildings meeting part of their energy demand. Organic photovoltaics have currently low cost and low efficiency while future technological innovations could increase their cost-effectiveness and promote their use in commercial applications.

ELECTRICITY DEMAND IN THE ISLAND OF CRETE

The electricity demand in the island of Crete is going to increase for several reasons. The clean energy transition in the island and the achievement of net-zero emissions target by 2050 requires the electrification of the heating and cooling sector as well as the insular transportation sector using electric vehicles. The electricity generation by fossil fuels and by renewable energies in Crete in 2018 is presented in table 2. Assuming a 3% annual increase in the electricity demand in Crete the power requirements in the island are presented in table 3. The current isolation of the island's electric grid limits the development of the abundant local renewable energy sources for heat and power generation. Fortunately, the interconnection of the electric grid of Crete with the Greek continental grid is going to be finalized by 2025 allowing the development of new solar and wind energy installations in the island.

Table 2. Electricity Generation from Renewable Energies and Fossil Fuels in Crete (2018)

Energy technology	Installed capacity (MW)	Electricity generation (MWh)	%, of electricity generation
Wind farms	200	510,059	16.76
Solar-PV systems (sited on fields)	78		
Solar-PV systems (sited on rooftops)	18		
Solar-PV systems (total)	96	134,808	4.43
Hydro power	0.6	256.8	0.01
Biogas burning	-	-	-
Total renewable energies	297.6	645,124	21.20
Thermal power plants using fuel and diesel oil	824.6	2,397,876	78.80
Total	1,122.2	3,043,000	100

Source: [24]

Table 3. Annual Electricity Demand in Crete until 2030

Year	Electricity demand (GWh)
2018	3,043
2019	3,134
2020	3,228
2021	3,325
2022	3,425
2023	3,528
2024	3,634
2025	3,733
2026	3,845
2027	3,960
2028	4,079
2029	4,201
2030	4,327

Source: own estimations

Mitigating climate change consists of a big challenge for the humanity while Europe as well as Greece are in the forefront of this effort. The future transition to a net-zero carbon economy requires the installation of various renewable energy systems producing green energy replacing the use of fossil fuels. The Greek national plan for energy and climate, 2023 foresees a large share of solar electricity in the country's energy mix until 2050 which gives an indication of the rapid growth of solar electricity generation in Greece as well as in Crete where the solar irradiance is high. The forecast of the required solar-PV systems in Greece until 2050 according to the Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate (2023) is presented in table 4.

Table 4. Forecast of the Required Solar-PV Systems in Greece until 2025 According to the Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate (2023)

Year	Solar-PV power (GWp)
2025	8.2
2030	13.4
2035	18.7
2040	25.4
2045	35.2
2050	40.3

Source: [35]

Estimation of the required land area in Crete for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems meeting the annual power demand

It has been indicated [37] that solar and wind power generation requires more land area than conventional energy generation technologies. The required land area in Crete for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems generating all the energy demand in the island is evaluated taking into account: a) the electricity demand in Crete, b) the yield of solar-PV modules in the island, and c) the land area coverage of solar-PV systems. Several characteristics of the island of Crete are presented in table 5.

Table 5. Several Characteristics of the Island of Crete

Parameter	Value
Area	833,600 ha
Population	624,408 inhabitants (census 2021)
Main economic activity	Tourism, generating more than 50% of the regional domestic product
Electric grid	Currently isolated, the interconnection with the grid of continental Greece with two undersea electric cables is under implementation
Potential of renewable energy sources	Very high in solar and wind energy resources
Annual electricity generation from conventional ground-mounted silicon solar-PV modules without tracking system	1,500-1,600 KWh/KWp

Source: own estimations, [41]

The required land area for the installation of several renewable energy technologies is presented in table 6.

Table 6. Required Land Area for the Installation of Several Renewable Energy Technologies

Technology	Required land area– Km ² /GW	Required land area– m ² /GWh
Flat-plate solar-PV systems	10-50	5,000-25,000
Wind turbines	100	140,000
Biomass	1,000	500,000
Solar thermal systems	20-50	10,000-20,000

Source: [16]

Taking into account that the electricity demand in Crete in 2025 will reach at 3,733 GWh (table 3) and the annual electricity yield from conventional solar-PV modules is at 1,600 KWh/KWp (table 5) the required nominal power of the solar photovoltaic systems for the generation of the electricity demand in Crete in 2025 is evaluated at 2,333.1 MWp. Assuming that the required land for the installation of solar photovoltaics is 20 Km²/GWp (table 6) the necessary land area for the installation

of solar-PV panels with nominal capacity at 2,33 GWp is evaluated at 46.6 Km² or 4,660 ha. Taking into account that the surface of Crete is at 833,600 ha (table 5) it is estimated that the required land area for the installation of the solar photovoltaic systems corresponds at 0.56% of the island's surface. Comparison of the requirements regarding the necessary land area for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems meeting all the electricity demand in several territories worldwide are presented in table 7.

Table 7. Necessary Land Area for the Installation of Solar Photovoltaic Systems Meeting All the Electricity Demand in Several Territories

Country, Territory	%, of total power demand, (year)	Land occupation for the installation of solar power plants (%)	Reference
EU, India, Japan, South Korea	25-80, (2050)	0.5-5.0	Dirk-Jan van de Ven et al, 2021
USA	100, (2023)	0.6	Center for Sustainable Systems, University of Michigan, 2023
USA	100, (2004)	0.4	The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA, 2004
Global average	100, (2023)	0.3	PV – Magazine, 1/2/12023
Island of Mykonos, Greece	100, (2023)	2.8	Nasioula et al, 2023
Island of Crete	100, (2025)	0.56	Present study, 2024

Source: various authors

The required land area for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems meeting the annual power demand in Crete in 2025 is presented in table 8.

Table 8. Required Land Area for the Installation of the Solar Photovoltaic Systems Meeting the Annual Power Demand in Crete (2025)

Annual energy demand in Crete in 2025	3,733 GWh
Population in Crete	624,408 inhabitants (census 2021)
Nominal power of the required solar photovoltaics for meeting the energy demand	2,333.1 MWp
Nominal power of solar-PVs per capita	2.33 KWp/capita
Installation cost of the solar-PVs (Unit cost = 1,000 €/KWp)	2.33 bill. €
Installation cost of solar-PVs per capita	2,333 €/capita
Required land area for the installation of the required solar-PV systems	4,660 ha
Required land area per capita	7.5 m ² /capita
Total land area in Crete	833,600 ha
Share of the land area for the installation of the required solar-PV systems to total land area in Crete	0.56%

Source: own estimations

DISCUSSION

The required land area for the installation of solar photovoltaics systems meeting the electricity demand in 2025 in the island of Crete, Greece has been estimated. It has been found that it corresponds at 0.56 % of the total surface of Crete. This percentage is in the range of 0.3-5.0% indicated in the literature for several territories worldwide (table 7). Our results indicate that the required land area for meeting the electricity demand in the island consists of only a small part of its total surface. Therefore, solar energy systems can generate all the electricity demand in Crete using only a small fraction of its land area without affecting its use for other activities. Many small-size and medium-size solar-PV systems have been already installed in Crete either on the rooftops of buildings or mounted on the ground. It should be noted though that a significant part of Crete consists of mountainous areas which are not suitable for installing solar photovoltaic systems. However, our results do not evaluate the percentage of valuable land area used for food and animal feed

production in Crete that would be needed for the installation of the required solar photovoltaic systems. They do not also indicate the percentage of the protected land area in Crete that would be needed for the installation of the abovementioned solar photovoltaic systems. A significant part of the required solar-PV capacity can be installed on the rooftops of several private and public buildings in the island while our work has not evaluated the nominal power of the solar photovoltaic systems which can be installed on the rooftop of buildings. Further work should be focused in the estimation of: a) the percentage of the valuable agricultural land area in the island which would be needed for the installation of the required solar-PV systems, b) the percentage of the protected and preserved land area in Crete which would be needed for the installation of the required solar-PV systems, and c) The surface of the buildings' rooftops in Crete that would be needed for the installation of the abovementioned solar-PV systems.

CONCLUSIONS

The land area which is required for the installation of solar photovoltaic systems generating the necessary electricity to meet the electricity demand in 2025 in Crete has been evaluated. The share of the land area required for the installation of these solar-PV systems to total land area in Crete has been also estimated. The electricity demand in 2025 in Crete has been evaluated at 3,733 GWh and the nominal power of the solar-PV systems required to generate the same amount of electricity at 2,333.1 MWp. The total installation cost of the required solar-PV systems has been evaluated at 2.33 bill. € or 2,333 €/capita. Therefore, if each resident of Crete will invest 2,333 € for the installation of solar-PV systems, for instance through energy cooperatives, self-sufficiency in electricity generation in the island would be achieved using the abundant local solar energy resources. The land area which is required for the installation of the abovementioned solar photovoltaic systems has been estimated at 4,660 ha or 7.5 m²/capita corresponding at 0.56% of the total surface in the island. Our results could be useful to policy makers and to local authorities who are willing to avoid or to limit the use of valuable fertile land area used in agriculture as well as the use of land areas which should be protected and preserved for the installation of solar-PV systems in Crete. Instead of installing solar-PV systems on fertile and cultivated land, they can be sited on degraded and uncultivated land areas which are not used in agriculture as well as on rooftops of several buildings.

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